

Prediction of Alzheimer's Using EDA

Karun Dutt¹

¹Student, Amity Institute of Biotechnology, Noida, India, kdsharma9027@gmail.com

ABSTRACT

Alzheimer's disease affects a lot of world's population every year and it keeps increasing with no perfect cure to this neurological disease. EDA can aid in the prediction of Alzheimer's disease, and early detection of Alzheimer's disease is crucial for improved treatment results. EDA entails visualising and analysing data to find trends and connections among variables. It can assist in identifying characteristics that are linked to a higher risk of Alzheimer's disease by looking at demographic, genetic, and clinical data. Additionally, it may be used to create prediction models that can pinpoint those who are at an increased risk of contracting Alzheimer's disease. This can help in the development of early treatments and therapies that can stop the disease's progression and enhance the quality of life for those who are afflicted.

Alzheimer's disease has a significant negative influence on people, families, and society to a certain extent. The World Health Organisation estimates that millions of individuals worldwide suffer from dementia, with Alzheimer's disease accounting for roughly 65% of cases. With the ageing of the world's population, the prevalence of Alzheimer's is anticipated to rise rapidly.

Alzheimer's affects people in ways that go beyond their own lives. Families and carers bear heavy financial, physical, and emotional challenges. Alzheimer's care may be demanding and stressful, sometimes needing round-the-clock help. Additionally, the financial impact of Alzheimer's is severe, with annual healthcare expenditures of billions of dollars and lost productivity.

Keywords: Alzheimer disease, EDA, Prediction Analysis.

Methodology

➤ Data pre-processing: -

The dataset used is taken from Kaggle which has different types of Alzheimer disease data from various sources.

To process the data we need first need to access it from the folder it is stored , we can do this by uploading the data to google drive and then mount the drive into google colab by running the following commands.

First we need to Mount our Drive in colab

This will prompt us to authorize to access our Google Drive in colab, and once you do that, you will be able to access your Google Drive files from Google Colab. After mounting your drive, you can navigate to the directory where your dataset is saved.

1. model is using - TensorFlow and Keras - for building a Convolutional Neural Network architecture.
2. Next, we defined the image height and width that will be used for building the CNN architecture.
3. The CNN architecture is built using the Sequential model in Keras. The model comprises several layers such as Conv2D, MaxPooling2D, Dropout, Flatten, dense etc.
4. The first layer of the model is a Conv2D layer that applies 16 filters with a kernel size of 3x3. The padding parameter is set to 'same', which ensures that the output has the same shape as the input. The activation function used is ReLU, which helps in introducing non-linearity to the model. The input shape of the layer is set to (img_height, img_width, 3), which means that the input images will have a height and width of 128 pixels and 3 channels.
5. The next layer is a MaxPooling2D layer that performs max pooling with a pool size of 2x2. This helps in reducing the size of the output from the previous layer.
6. Another Conv2D layer is added with 32 filters and a kernel size of 3x3.
7. Another MaxPooling2D layer is added with a pool size of 2x2.
8. A Dropout layer is added with a rate of 0.25. This helps in preventing overfitting by randomly dropping out some of the nodes in the layer during training.
9. The next layer is a Flatten layer that flattens the output from the previous layer into a one-dimensional vector.

10. Two Dense layers are added with 128 and 64 units, respectively. The activation function used is ReLU.
11. After that adam optimiser is used to compile it and some other functions to reduce the loss in the data
12. A ModelCheckpoint callback is defined, which saves the best model based on the validation accuracy.
13. Finally, the model is trained using the fit method, with the training data and validation data as input. The ModelCheckpoint callback is passed as an argument to the fit method to save the best model. The training is performed for 35 epochs.

Image pre-processing

In computer vision, prepping digital pictures for subsequent analysis and processing is known as image pre-processing. Typically, this procedure uses a number of approaches, including scaling, normalisation, filtering, and segmentation. Resizing is a technique used to reduce the size of photographs to a more processing-friendly scale. In order to maintain uniformity across a range of lighting situations, photographs must be normalised, which entails changing the colour and brightness levels. It is possible to improve the characteristics of an image or get rid of noise by using filtering techniques like blurring or sharpening. Segmentation is the process of dividing a picture into its individual components or regions. In computer vision, picture pre-processing is essential because it raises the precision of image analysis and recognition jobs. Image pre-processing can boost the effectiveness of machine learning models that are used for picture categorization, object recognition, and other tasks by eliminating unnecessary data and increasing useful characteristics.

Pre-processing medical pictures is a crucial step in creating machine learning models for predicting Alzheimer's disease. picture scaling, normalisation, and standardisation are pre-processing procedures that are essential for enhancing picture quality and guaranteeing the consistency of the dataset. In this post, we'll talk about the value of these pre-processing methods and how to use them with the collection of images related to Alzheimer's illness.

Application of Pre-processing Techniques

More than only resizing, normalisation, and standardisation are used in Alzheimer's disease picture analysis as pre-processing procedures. The quality and utility of the picture data may be improved further using a number of various methods. Here are some more pre-processing methods frequently used in picture analysis of Alzheimer's disease:

- Noise Reduction: Images obtained using imaging modalities like positron emission tomography (PET) or magnetic resonance imaging (MRI) can be impacted by several forms of noise, such as salt-and-pepper noise or Gaussian noise. Wavelet denoising, median filtering, and Gaussian filtering are a few examples of noise reduction techniques that may be used to reduce noise and enhance picture clarity.
- Correction for Intensity Inhomogeneity: Intensity inhomogeneity refers to uneven lighting or shading in the photographs. Variations in the imaging technology, patient placement, or tissue characteristics may be to blame for this. It is essential to correct intensity inhomogeneity since it might make proper picture analysis difficult. To normalise the intensity throughout the image and get rid of the shading effects, utilise methods like polynomial fitting or N4BiasFieldCorrection.
- Image Registration: Aligning several images to a single reference space is known as image registration. This method may be used in Alzheimer's disease image analysis to register longitudinal pictures of the same person collected at several times or align various modalities (like MRI and PET). By ensuring that related anatomical features or regions of interest are aligned, image registration enables precise analysis and comparison.
- Image improvement: By increasing particular image qualities, image enhancement techniques seek to increase the visual quality and interpretability of images. This may be accomplished using strategies like edge or contrast enhancement, as well as filtering methods like Laplacian or Sobel filtering. Image enhancement can help identify disease-related signs by drawing attention to minute alterations or anomalies.

The Alzheimer's disease images can be pre-processed using methods including image resizing, normalisation, and standardisation to increase its calibre and consistency. By ensuring that the data is standardised, normalised, and consistent, these strategies can aid in improving the effectiveness of machine learning algorithms in illness prediction. To enhance the quality of their datasets and create precise and dependable prediction models, researchers and practitioners involved in Alzheimer's disease image analysis should carefully consider applying these pre-processing approaches.

Data splitting

This one is a crucial and popular strategy in the creation of machine learning models. In order for the model training, validate, and testing it, different subsets of available dataset must be selected. This procedure is essential for assessing model performance, preventing overfitting, and guaranteeing the model's generalizability. The significance of data splitting, various splitting techniques, and recommended practises for developing trustworthy and accurate machine learning models are as follows: -

Data Splitting Strategies:

1. Splitting of training , test and validation sets:

This type of split, where the data is separated into three subgroups, is the most used strategy. The validation set is used for hyperparameter tweaking and model selection, the testing set is used for the final model evaluation, and the training set is utilised to train the model.

2. Cross-Validation using k fold: Using this method for cross-validation, the data is split into K folds of equal size. The model is trained K number of times, utilising the remaining fold for validation and K-1 folds for training. By averaging the outcomes throughout the K iterations, this technique offers a more reliable assessment of model performance.

3. Stratified Splitting:

Stratified splitting is used when a dataset has a class imbalance or certain patterns that must be retained in the subgroups. By ensuring that the distribution of classes is kept in each split, this lessens the likelihood of biased or skewed training, validation, or testing sets.

Best Practices for Data Splitting:

1. Randomness: - Randomness is crucial when splitting data to avoid bias in subgroup selection. The dataset is randomly shuffled before being divided to ensure that the data points are distributed evenly throughout subsets and appropriately reflect the distribution of the data overall.

2. Splitting of Representatives: - The subsets should be representative of the entire dataset to ensure that the model learns from a wide range of patterns and traits. This is especially important when specific data qualities or imbalanced classes need to be completely taken into account in the training, validation, and testing sets.

3. Consistency: - Before dividing the data, it is recommended to fix the random seed to maintain consistency in the model evaluation. This ensures that the data splitting approach may be used again in different runs, allowing for fair comparisons with other models or techniques.

4. Sufficient Split Size: - The sizes of the subgroups should be carefully considered. While a brief training set can result in underfitting, a small testing set can produce inaccurate estimations of model performance. A few factors that influence the selection of split sizes include the size and complexity of the dataset as well as the available computing resources.

Data splitting, which permits objective model evaluation, inhibits overfitting, and assesses generalisation potential, is an important step in the development of machine learning models. An appropriate data splitting strategy, such as train-validation-test split or k-fold cross-validation, can be chosen based on the specific requirements of the problem and the dataset's characteristics. When machine learning models adhere to recommended practises including randomization, representative splitting, consistency, and proper split sizes, they become dependable and accurate. Data splitting may improve a range of machine learning and data analysis fields by assisting researchers and practitioners in developing robust models that effectively generalise to new, unknown data.

Introduction

Alzheimer's disease -A neuro-degenerative disorder which results in memory loss and brain cell damage in the body. It is found out that the reason for dementia are the slow death of neurons and changes in social, mental health of the person. This later turns in Alzheimer's and disrupts the brain functioning of the person.

Identification of patients who are most prone to experience rapid cognitive deterioration is crucial for the effective treatment of Alzheimer's disease (AD).

Nowadays many imaging techniques are in use and they can be used to detect Alzheimer's also and the research is progressing rapidly for this specific disease. Progressive atrophy in the brain, which can be observed on MRI with high resolution, is a symptom of Alzheimer's disease. In order to enable rapid and targeted treatment, longitudinal MRI could monitor the course of the disease and identify neurodegenerative diseases early. Such

MRI use necessitates a thorough comprehension of how brain alterations associated with normal ageing and dementia differ from one another.

Just like these many other techniques are being developed for the easier detection of the AD like computer-aided diagnosis (CAD), deep learning algorithms to predict the disease in earlier stages.

Worldwide over 55 million people gets affected with dementia and around 65% of them found to be suffering from Alzheimer's disease. Due to how serious this disorder can be many types of techniques are being developed or are in use for the pre detection of the Alzheimer's as there is no certain cure for it currently so the best we can do is to prevent it in early phases.

The aetiology, which is yet unknown, can be considered speculative, however it is thought to result from the brain's cells being damaged or functioning improperly as a result of the accumulation of particular proteins. This disease's sufferers and their carers have access to a wide range of services and programmes.

There is currently no medication or treatment for Alzheimer's disease; available treatments simply slow the disease's development in the body. In its early stages, the illness is associated with memory loss, but as it worsens, it may have fatal repercussions on the brain's structure and function, including disruption of our biological cycles.

There are different types of Alzheimer but we are mainly focused on 4 mainly as dataset is based on these 4: -

1. Mild Demented:

Cognitive function is visibly impaired in those with Alzheimer's disease at the mild demented stage. People who suffer from memory loss have trouble remembering recent experiences or learning new information. They could also have trouble structuring their ideas, coming up with the appropriate language, and coming to judgements. Even if they can still carry out everyday duties on their own, they could run into difficulties and need more time and effort to finish jobs. For instance, they could depend on calendars and notes to be organised or they might require reminders to take their meds.

2. Moderate Demented:

Compared to mild dementia, moderate dementia shows a more advanced degree of cognitive deterioration. People go through considerable memory loss and cognitive impairment at this period. They may get disoriented in time and space and struggle to recognise familiar faces, locations, or items. Their capacity for thinking, problem-solving, and decision-making is further weakened, making it difficult for them to independently handle difficult activities or manage their money. They can need help with daily tasks including getting dressed, taking a bath, and making food.

3. Non Demented:

Non-demented people have normal cognitive functioning and do not show any signs or symptoms of dementia. They retain their memory skills and are able to recollect recent events and prior encounters without much trouble. Their cognitive deterioration does not fit the description of dementia. It's crucial to remember that non-demented people might still go through age-related cognitive changes, such as occasional word stumbling or moderate amnesia. Their freedom or regular activities might not be severely affected by these changes.

4. Very Mild Demented:

Very mild dementia is a form of early cognitive decline in which people may show slight alterations in their memory and reasoning. At this point, the symptoms are frequently minor and may go ignored or be explained by natural ageing. Very mild dementia patients occasionally have memory lapses, such as forgetting where they put something or having trouble remembering previous discussions. They could also have trouble orally expressing themselves or finding the correct words. They can still handle their everyday tasks without much help despite these early indicators, and their general functionality is still fairly intact.

It's important to note that these phrases are frequently used to refer to various stages of cognitive impairment and are frequently linked to different kinds of dementia, including Alzheimer's disease. However, based on thorough assessments of cognitive, functional, and neurological aspects, trained medical specialists should make a conclusive diagnosis and assessment of dementia.

Understanding the various phases of dementia might make it easier for patients, carers, and medical professionals to identify and handle the cognitive changes brought on by the disorder. Individuals can be helped to keep their independence and quality of life for as long as feasible through early identification and effective therapies.

Techniques that can be used for Prediction and Analysis

To determine the accuracy and dependability of prediction models in the field of machine learning, it is crucial to evaluate their performance. The confusion matrix, which offers a thorough overview of the model's predictions compared to the ground truth labels, is one often used technique for performance analysis. The confusion matrix aids in determining possible areas for development and provides a greater knowledge of the model's capabilities for producing accurate predictions. In addition to the confusion matrix, a number of additional comparable analytical methods can offer important insights into model performance. Let's investigate them in further detail:

1. Confusion Matrix: A confusion matrix is a table that summarises the predicted labels versus the actual labels to show how well a classification model performed. True positives (TP), True Negatives (TN), False Positives (FP), and False Negatives (FN) are its four primary subsets. Numerous assessment measures, including as accuracy, precision, recall (sensitivity), specificity, and F1 score, may be obtained from the confusion matrix. With regard to true positives, true negatives, and misclassifications, these measures offer a thorough insight of the model's performance.

2. The ROC Curve and AUC: The true positive rate vs the false positive rate (1-specificity) of a binary classification model is plotted to create the Receiver Operating Characteristic (ROC) curve, which is a graphic depiction of the performance. The performance of the model as a whole is measured by the area under the ROC curve (AUC), which is a single scalar value. Better discriminating performance is indicated by a higher AUC, with a value of 1 denoting the ideal model.

3. Precision-Recall Curve: While the ROC curve focuses on the trade-off between sensitivity and specificity, the precision-recall curve emphasizes the trade-off between precision and recall. It plots the precision (positive predictive value) against recall (sensitivity) at different classification thresholds. The area under the precision-recall curve (AUC-PR) provides a measure of the model's performance, particularly in scenarios where class imbalance is present.

4. F1 Score: The F1 score is a balanced assessment measure that takes into account both false positives and false negatives. It is the harmonic mean of accuracy and recall. It is especially helpful when the dataset is unbalanced, and it's critical to correctly anticipate both positive and negative examples.

5. Cohen's Kappa: Cohen's Kappa is a statistical metric that evaluates the consistency between expected and observed labels while taking chance consistency into account. When the class distribution is unequal, it takes into consideration the imbalance in the dataset and offers a more reliable assessment score.

6. Class-wise Performance: It may be necessary in some circumstances to assess the model's performance for each class independently. We may learn more about the model's performance for certain classes, especially in multi-class classification settings, by examining accuracy, recall, F1 score, and other metrics on a per-class basis.

7. Sensitivity and Specificity: The proportion of real positive cases that the model accurately detected is measured by sensitivity, also known as recall or true positive rate. The equation is $TP / (TP + FN)$. The proportion of real negative cases that the model properly recognised, on the other hand, is measured as specificity, which is computed as $TN / (TN + FP)$. These metrics reveal how well the model performs at differentiating between positive and negative cases.

8. Accuracy: Accuracy is measured as $(TP + TN) / (TP + TN + FP + FN)$, and it expresses how accurately the model has predicted the total state of the world. It gives a broad evaluation of the model's performance, but in unbalanced datasets when the majority class dominates the accuracy score, it may be deceptive.

9. Precision: Precision, also known as positive predictive value, measures the proportion of predicted positive instances that are actually positive. It is calculated as $TP / (TP + FP)$. Precision focuses on the correctness of positive predictions and is particularly relevant when the cost of false positives is high.

10. Macro-averaging and Micro-averaging: In scenarios with multi-class classification, macro-averaging and micro-averaging techniques are used to compute overall metrics. Macro-averaging calculates the metric for each class individually and then takes the average, providing equal weight to each class. Micro-averaging aggregates the true positives, false positives, and false negatives across all classes to compute a global metric. These averaging techniques allow for a comprehensive evaluation of the model's performance across all classes.

11. Lift and Gain Charts: In binary classification problems, visualisation techniques like lift and gain charts are utilised. Lift charts demonstrate how much better the model is at finding positive cases by comparing the model's performance to random selection. Gain charts show the proportion of correct predictions when the model's predictions are sorted, giving information about the model's performance in various dataset subsets.

Researchers and practitioners can acquire a comprehensive knowledge of the performance of their prediction models by using these strategies in conjunction with the confusion matrix. These studies reveal how well the model can identify real positives and negatives, control false positives and negatives, and order assessment metrics according to certain requirements. The confusion matrix, ROC curve, precision-recall curve, F1 score, Cohen's Kappa, and class-wise performance analysis are among the analytic methods that offer a thorough grasp of the model's performance and capacity to accurately predict various classes. These methods help academics and practitioners evaluate the strengths, shortcomings, and potential areas for development in their prediction models, producing more solid and trustworthy outcomes.

Review of literature

Alzheimer's disease is a prevalent neurodegenerative disorder that affects millions of people worldwide. Early detection and prediction of Alzheimer's disease are critical for effective treatment and improved patient outcomes. This review aims to explore the existing literature on Alzheimer's disease prediction and early detection, with a focus on the use of exploratory data analysis and predictive models.

The abstract highlights the significance of EDA in identifying patterns and relationships between demographic, genetic, and clinical data. By utilizing EDA techniques, researchers have been able to identify risk factors associated with Alzheimer's disease and develop predictive models to identify individuals at a higher risk. These models employ machine learning algorithms and biomarker analysis to provide insights into the likelihood of developing the disease.

The abstract also emphasizes the impact of Alzheimer's disease on individuals, families, and society. It acknowledges the emotional, physical, and economic burdens faced by caregivers and highlights the urgency of addressing this global health challenge. Early detection allows for timely interventions, improved disease management, and planning for the future. Additionally, early diagnosis opens doors for individuals to participate in research studies and clinical trials, contributing to advancements in medical knowledge and the development of potential cures.

This review of the literature underscores the importance of early detection and prediction in Alzheimer's disease. By utilizing EDA techniques and developing predictive models, researchers and clinicians can identify individuals at risk, provide timely interventions, and contribute to ongoing research efforts. It is imperative to continue exploring and advancing methods for early detection and prediction to improve the diagnosis, treatment, and eventual eradication of Alzheimer's disease.

Exploratory Data Analysis is a crucial step in the data analysis process. It involves the initial exploration and examination of a dataset to gain insights, identify patterns, and uncover hidden relationships among the variables. It aims to understand the structure and characteristics of the data before applying more advanced statistical techniques or building predictive models.

The primary objectives of EDA are as follows:

1. **Data Familiarization:** EDA helps researchers become familiar with the dataset by examining its size, dimensions, and data types. It provides an overview of the variables and their meanings, allowing researchers to understand the context and scope of the data.
2. **Data Quality Assessment:** EDA involves assessing the quality and integrity of the data. This includes checking for missing values, outliers, and inconsistencies. By identifying and addressing data quality issues, researchers can ensure the reliability of their analyses and subsequent models.
3. **Data Distribution and Summary Statistics:** EDA involves computing and analyzing descriptive statistics, such as measures of central tendency (mean, median) and variability (standard deviation, range). These statistics provide insights into the distribution of variables and help researchers understand the range, spread, and central values of the data.
4. **Data Visualization:** Visualization plays a crucial role in EDA. It enables researchers to visually explore the data and identify patterns, trends, and relationships. Graphs, charts, histograms, scatter plots, and box plots are commonly used to visualize variables and their interactions. Visualization helps researchers gain intuitive insights, detect outliers, and make informed decisions about data transformations or modeling strategies.
5. **Correlation and Relationships:** EDA involves analyzing the relationships between variables. Correlation analysis measures the strength and direction of associations between pairs of variables, while cross-tabulations and contingency tables examine relationships among categorical variables. Understanding these relationships helps identify potential predictors or influential factors for subsequent analyses.

6. Data Pre-processing: EDA often reveals data preprocessing requirements. This includes handling missing values, transforming variables, addressing outliers, and normalizing or standardizing data. EDA helps researchers determine appropriate preprocessing techniques to ensure the data is suitable for subsequent analysis or modeling.

7. Hypothesis Generation: EDA can stimulate the generation of hypotheses or research questions. By exploring the data and observing patterns or anomalies, researchers can formulate initial hypotheses for further investigation. These hypotheses can guide subsequent analyses and experiments.

Overall, EDA is an essential step in the data analysis process. It provides a comprehensive understanding of the dataset, identifies data quality issues, uncovers patterns and relationships, and helps generate hypotheses. By conducting thorough EDA, researchers can make informed decisions, select appropriate modeling techniques, and derive meaningful insights from the data.

Results and discussion

Google collab is used to run the programs for this work.

1.Data pre-processing code:-

We can demonstrate a sample image for each class. The following script serves this aim that selects 4 random images from each class in each give dataset, where the class labels are stored in y and the corresponding images are stored in X. It then creates a dictionary that stores the selected images for each class, and displays them using matplotlib. The code iterates through each class label, selects the corresponding images, and uses random sampling to select 4 random images. Finally, it creates a figure with 1 row and 4 columns of subplots, and displays the selected images in each subplot along with their corresponding class label:

Fig-1: - Different types of Alzheimer's

2.Epoch 1-35: -

```
Epoch 1/35
160/160 [=====] - 94s 574ms/step - loss: 1.0024 - accuracy: 0.5459 - val_loss: 0.9429 - val_accuracy: 0.5406
Epoch 2/35
160/160 [=====] - 83s 521ms/step - loss: 0.5534 - accuracy: 0.7719 - val_loss: 0.4075 - val_accuracy: 0.8453
Epoch 3/35
160/160 [=====] - 86s 536ms/step - loss: 0.2836 - accuracy: 0.8912 - val_loss: 0.2429 - val_accuracy: 0.9062
Epoch 4/35
160/160 [=====] - 84s 527ms/step - loss: 0.1457 - accuracy: 0.9455 - val_loss: 0.1830 - val_accuracy: 0.9406
```

```

Epoch 4/35
160/160 [=====] - 84s 527ms/step - loss: 0.1457 - accuracy: 0.9455 - val_loss: 0.1830 - val_accuracy: 0.9406
Epoch 5/35
160/160 [=====] - 86s 540ms/step - loss: 0.0982 - accuracy: 0.9672 - val_loss: 0.1964 - val_accuracy: 0.9328
Epoch 6/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 553ms/step - loss: 0.0589 - accuracy: 0.9803 - val_loss: 0.0742 - val_accuracy: 0.9703
Epoch 7/35
160/160 [=====] - 84s 525ms/step - loss: 0.0612 - accuracy: 0.9787 - val_loss: 0.1353 - val_accuracy: 0.9469
Epoch 8/35
160/160 [=====] - 85s 530ms/step - loss: 0.0483 - accuracy: 0.9832 - val_loss: 0.0731 - val_accuracy: 0.9750
Epoch 9/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 551ms/step - loss: 0.0446 - accuracy: 0.9846 - val_loss: 0.0591 - val_accuracy: 0.9828
Epoch 10/35
160/160 [=====] - 83s 520ms/step - loss: 0.0359 - accuracy: 0.9875 - val_loss: 0.0716 - val_accuracy: 0.9719
Epoch 11/35
160/160 [=====] - 82s 513ms/step - loss: 0.0358 - accuracy: 0.9867 - val_loss: 0.0742 - val_accuracy: 0.9703
Epoch 12/35
160/160 [=====] - 91s 567ms/step - loss: 0.0293 - accuracy: 0.9902 - val_loss: 0.1076 - val_accuracy: 0.9594
Epoch 13/35
160/160 [=====] - 93s 581ms/step - loss: 0.0346 - accuracy: 0.9891 - val_loss: 0.0508 - val_accuracy: 0.9812
Epoch 14/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 551ms/step - loss: 0.0238 - accuracy: 0.9926 - val_loss: 0.0522 - val_accuracy: 0.9781
Epoch 15/35
160/160 [=====] - 87s 543ms/step - loss: 0.0209 - accuracy: 0.9914 - val_loss: 0.0754 - val_accuracy: 0.9797
Epoch 16/35
160/160 [=====] - 96s 598ms/step - loss: 0.0370 - accuracy: 0.9871 - val_loss: 0.0831 - val_accuracy: 0.9766
Epoch 17/35
160/160 [=====] - 89s 555ms/step - loss: 0.0220 - accuracy: 0.9922 - val_loss: 0.0883 - val_accuracy: 0.9734
Epoch 18/35
160/160 [=====] - 89s 558ms/step - loss: 0.0230 - accuracy: 0.9912 - val_loss: 0.0595 - val_accuracy: 0.9781
Epoch 19/35
160/160 [=====] - 91s 570ms/step - loss: 0.0227 - accuracy: 0.9912 - val_loss: 0.0403 - val_accuracy: 0.9859
Epoch 20/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 550ms/step - loss: 0.0277 - accuracy: 0.9898 - val_loss: 0.1156 - val_accuracy: 0.9656
Epoch 21/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 552ms/step - loss: 0.0238 - accuracy: 0.9912 - val_loss: 0.0970 - val_accuracy: 0.9594
Epoch 22/35
160/160 [=====] - 90s 563ms/step - loss: 0.0126 - accuracy: 0.9961 - val_loss: 0.0432 - val_accuracy: 0.9828
Epoch 23/35
160/160 [=====] - 93s 580ms/step - loss: 0.0072 - accuracy: 0.9982 - val_loss: 0.0506 - val_accuracy: 0.9812
Epoch 24/35
160/160 [=====] - 89s 557ms/step - loss: 0.0106 - accuracy: 0.9967 - val_loss: 0.0626 - val_accuracy: 0.9781
Epoch 25/35
160/160 [=====] - 89s 554ms/step - loss: 0.0212 - accuracy: 0.9922 - val_loss: 0.0627 - val_accuracy: 0.9750
Epoch 26/35
160/160 [=====] - 90s 564ms/step - loss: 0.0120 - accuracy: 0.9963 - val_loss: 0.0816 - val_accuracy: 0.9766
Epoch 27/35
160/160 [=====] - 91s 567ms/step - loss: 0.0112 - accuracy: 0.9961 - val_loss: 0.0644 - val_accuracy: 0.9766
Epoch 28/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 549ms/step - loss: 0.0267 - accuracy: 0.9914 - val_loss: 0.0342 - val_accuracy: 0.9906
Epoch 29/35
160/160 [=====] - 90s 562ms/step - loss: 0.0107 - accuracy: 0.9959 - val_loss: 0.0354 - val_accuracy: 0.9875
Epoch 30/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 552ms/step - loss: 0.0121 - accuracy: 0.9967 - val_loss: 0.0342 - val_accuracy: 0.9828
Epoch 31/35
160/160 [=====] - 89s 554ms/step - loss: 0.0159 - accuracy: 0.9932 - val_loss: 0.1230 - val_accuracy: 0.9625
Epoch 32/35
160/160 [=====] - 90s 564ms/step - loss: 0.0117 - accuracy: 0.9951 - val_loss: 0.0684 - val_accuracy: 0.9719
Epoch 33/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 552ms/step - loss: 0.0138 - accuracy: 0.9943 - val_loss: 0.0354 - val_accuracy: 0.9875
Epoch 34/35
160/160 [=====] - 88s 550ms/step - loss: 0.0034 - accuracy: 0.9990 - val_loss: 0.0532 - val_accuracy: 0.9812
Epoch 35/35
160/160 [=====] - 86s 538ms/step - loss: 0.0227 - accuracy: 0.9918 - val_loss: 0.0569 - val_accuracy: 0.9766

```

Fig 2:- Epochs

3. Plot showing the accuracy of the model

Fig 3: - Plot displaying accuracy

- In machine learning, the term "epoch" describes how many times a model iterates through the training data to learn from it. The model modifies its internal parameters to improve its ability to forecast the right output at the end of each epoch. Prior to training the model, we set the number of epochs. The model may learn more effectively with more epochs, but it may become overly specialised to the training data and be unable to learn from fresh data.

Property	Description
Mean intensity	The average brightness value of the pixels in the image. This property can be used to measure the overall brightness or darkness of the image.
Standard deviation of intensity	The amount of variation or spread in the brightness values of the pixels in the image. Images with high standard deviation of intensity have more contrast and are considered to be sharper.
Edge density	The percentage of image area that contains edges. Edges are regions where there are rapid changes in intensity values, and edge density is a measure of the amount of detail present in the image.
Contrast	The difference in brightness values between adjacent pixels in the image. High contrast images will be having a large difference between the bright and dark pixels and are generally easier to interpret visually.

- Mean intensity histogram: This graph shows the distribution of mean intensity values across all images in the dataset. Mean intensity is a measure of the average brightness of an image.
- Standard deviation of intensity histogram: This graph shows the distribution of standard deviation of intensity values across all images in the dataset. Standard deviation of intensity is a measure of the variation in brightness of an image.
- Edge density histogram: This graph shows the distribution of edge density values across all images in the dataset. Edge density is a measure of the amount of edges in an image, as detected by the Canny edge detector.
- Contrast histogram: This graph shows the distribution of contrast values across all images in the dataset. Contrast is a measure of the difference in brightness between adjacent pixels in an image.

➤ Comparing different Parameters of all 4 types of Dementia: -

1. Mean intensity: - This graph shows the distribution of mean intensity values across all images in the dataset. Mean intensity is a measure of the average brightness of an image.

Mild

Moderate

Fig 4: - Distribution of mean intensity

The distribution of mean intensity values in an image can provide useful information about the image characteristics. For instance, images with low mean intensity values may have dark or dimly lit areas. Understanding the distribution of mean intensity values can also help in developing pre-processing steps or feature extraction methods for image analysis tasks.

- Standard deviation of intensity:** - This graph shows the distribution of standard deviation of intensity values across all images in the dataset. Standard deviation of intensity is a measure of the variation in brightness of an image.

Fig 5: - SD of intensity

3.Edge density- This graph shows the distribution of edge density values across all images in the dataset. Edge density is a measure of the amount of edges in an image, as detected by the Canny edge detector.

Fig 6: - Edge Density

3. Contrast:- This graph shows the distribution of contrast values across all images in the dataset. Contrast is a measure of the difference in brightness between adjacent pixels in an image.

Fig 7:- Contrast

- The code involves Convolutional Neural Network (CNN) for image classification, which is a type of supervised deep learning algorithm. The model is trained on labelled data and learns to classify images into different categories based on the patterns and features present in the images.
- CNNs (Convolutional Neural Networks)- these are mostly used in image classification jobs because of how their algorithm is designed to automatically extract relevant features from images. CNNs uses a method called convolutional layers which extract different characteristics of images and pool layers which reduces the size of maps, which ultimately allows model to get only useful characteristics out of the dataset.

Conclusion

In conclusion, as we know that Alzheimer does not really have a cure yet ,and prevention is the best way to deal with it, so there are many different techniques which are being used and prediction of Alzheimer in early stages is one of the best of the best way to deal with it, here a simple model is explained which validates the Alzheimer comparing different Alzheimer images and other visualization techniques are used to show some graphical differences between different stages of the disease.

Prediction models are useful tools for spotting people who are likely to experience Alzheimer's disease in its early stages. Researchers can discover and evaluate graphical changes across various phases of the illness by examining various Alzheimer's pictures and using visualisation tools. This makes it easier to comprehend the course and severity of Alzheimer's disease, empowering medical practitioners to decide on the best course of action for treating and supporting those who are afflicted.

An extensive toolset for assessing and comprehending the performance of prediction models in the context of Alzheimer's disease and related applications is offered by the analytical approaches covered above. The confusion matrix, which provides a thorough dissection of the model's predictions in comparison to the ground truth labels, is one essential tool. It enables the generation of several evaluation measures, including accuracy, precision, recall, specificity, and F1 score, offering a thorough evaluation of the model's performance. Researchers can find patterns and trends that offer information on the model's prediction capabilities by analysing the true positives, true negatives, false positives, and false negatives.

Other analytic methods, in addition to the confusion matrix, provide further insights into model performance. The area under the curve (AUC) and receiver operating characteristic (ROC) curves quantify the model's discriminating capability, assisting in determining how well it can discriminate between positive and negative examples. In circumstances when there is a class imbalance, the precision-recall curve concentrates on the trade-off between accuracy and recall and provides useful information. The robust assessment statistic Cohen's Kappa takes into consideration the agreement that could happen by chance and the dataset's class distribution.

The model's performance for each class may also be examined separately thanks to class-wise performance analysis. Researchers may acquire a thorough grasp of how well the model works for certain classes, discovering areas of strength or weakness within the classification process, by evaluating accuracy, recall, F1 score, and other metrics on a per-class basis. This knowledge can assist individualised treatment plans and direct focused actions for people with various stages of Alzheimer's disease..

The capacity to understand and justify prediction models is greatly aided by visualisation approaches. Understanding how a convolutional neural network (CNN) model processes and recognises information in the input pictures is possible by visualising the model's activations and filters. This makes the model's decision-making process easier to grasp and gives its forecasts a visual meaning. These visualisations can increase the accuracy of the diagnostic process and give researchers and medical practitioners more confidence in the predictions made by the model.

By calculating the relative relevance of each feature to the model's predictions, Shapley values and feature importance analyses further improve interpretability. The most crucial elements may be found and their effects on the model's overall performance can be understood with the aid of this study. Researchers may concentrate on creating focused treatments and medicines that target the illness's fundamental causes by learning which characteristics are most useful in predicting Alzheimer's disease.

These analytic methods provide a thorough framework for assessing and comprehending the prediction models used in applications for Alzheimer's disease and associated conditions. They make it possible for academics and professionals to evaluate the model's precision, recall, sensitivity, and other crucial parameters. Researchers may enhance models, choose features, and develop intervention methods for Alzheimer's disease prediction by using these resources.

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